

PHIRI

Population Health Information
Research Infrastructure

The future of Foresight: input for the PHIRI sustainability plan

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Henk Hilderink

Elizabeth Mutubuki

Daniela Moyer Holz

Marit de Vries

Mariken Tijhuis

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Introduction

Insight into future trends and developments is essential for the everyday work of policy makers. Foresight is a systematic, participatory, and vision-building process that explores the future with the aim to anticipate future trends and support present-day actions. The COVID-19 pandemic emphasized the importance of **Public Health Foresight Studies (PHFS)**. **PHFS** may be more necessary than ever to gain insight into possible future health impacts of pandemics, in the short and long term. These include changes in regular healthcare delivery, lifestyle and socio-economic developments. One of the objectives of PHIRI (Population Health Information Research Infrastructure, PHIRI.EU) was to support European Union Member States (EU MS) in conducting a public health foresight study in order to gain insights into possible future health impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Achievements within PHIRI

Within PHIRI, various activities were undertaken to support the objective to strengthen the knowledge, expertise and applications of foresight in the field of public health.

1. OVERVIEW OF CURRENT FORESIGHT ACTIVITIES IN EUROPE AND BEYOND

Through a literature review and a survey, we identified current foresight activities, gained knowledge regarding the capacity and need for foresight methodology. In addition, we were able to create a foresight network. Our inventory of foresight activities from the survey showed that, a few EU MS had an established capacity to conduct foresight studies. The survey shed light on the foresight capacity needs across EU MS, which served as basis to develop the foresight capacity building course.

2. CAPACITY BUILDING IN FORESIGHT

We developed a public health foresight course to level EU MS to a similar degree of knowledge in foresight, thereby strengthening European capacity in foresight. The course took place in 2021 and reached more than 70 public health professionals across 21 EU MS. The course consisted of three parts; an introductory module, a set of three advanced modules, and a final module synthesizing the lessons learned. A foresight methodology template and the course videos are available for public use, in order to strengthen foresight capacity.

3. USING THIS CAPACITY TO DEVELOP SCENARIOS

We developed the capacity building activity 'Develop your PHFS' in which participants from EU MS conducted their own foresight study with support from PHIRI. 'Develop your PHFS' took place throughout 2022, consisting of 12 guided sessions and resulting in 11 country presentations of planned foresight studies from 8 EU MS. Participants developed their knowledge, expertise, and capacity in public health foresight. This activity shed light into challenges that can be encountered during the planning and development of a foresight study and how to address such challenges.

4. DEVELOPING GUIDANCE IN IDENTIFYING PROMISING POLICY STRATEGIES

Based on the lessons learnt from the previous tasks, four policy briefs were developed. These policy briefs focused on the use of foresight in policy making, aimed at communicating with public health experts and policy makers on how foresight can provide a platform to explore the future and discuss possible solutions to address present and future challenges towards desirable futures. Three policy briefs provide specific examples on the use of foresight and resulting policy recommendations in mental health, climate and healthcare, and digitalization of healthcare.

SWOT assessment regarding foresight

Based on foresight activities, such as capacity building, application of foresight to country case studies and the link of foresight to policy making we have come to the following SWOT assessment of public health foresight.

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foresight provides a systematic way to support future thinking. • Foresight is an essential input for the policy making process. • There is a small but lively network of people involved in foresight. 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foresight requires substantial resources and a multi-disciplinary team to cover different aspects. • There is no blue print to do a foresight study (learning by doing).
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pandemic increased the demand for foresight to be better prepared for the future. • Public health foresight can learn from other frontrunners in the field of climate change and technology. • Many organization see the additional value of foresight and want to apply it. 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fragmentation of expertise. • Limited available resources to do a PHFS properly. • Link of foresight to policy making remains a challenge.

Sustain foresight in the future

For the sustainability of foresight in public health, several key next steps have been identified:

1. Further promotion of the use of PHIRI foresight materials (e.g. foresight training course, templates to guide doing a foresight study, tutorial).
2. Engage with organisations that actively apply foresight or have the ambition to do so (e.g. various national public health institutes, WHO, ECDC, OECD, etc).
3. Collaborate with other projects to make foresight a common element of research projects.
4. Secure long-term financial resources (e.g. lobby to make foresighting mandatory).
5. Engage with the current users' networks to further exchange knowledge and expertise (e.g. through EUPHA Section foresight).
6. Ensure visibility of foresight after the PHIRI funding period ends by keeping PHIRI newsletter and social media accounts active and promoting foresight through other projects.

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